

Development of high-performance and cost-effective electrode assembly for redox flow battery

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Redox flow battery (RFB) is a candidate for safe and durable stationary energy storage, however high CAPEX still obstructs its fast commercialization. In our contribution, we are addressing this challenge by the development of method for low-contact resistance connection (bonding) of the bipolar plate to both graphite felt electrodes and copper current collectors. Using own extruded bipolar plates with low carbon filling, two different manufacture methods were studied and optimized: hot-press and microwave welding. The electrode assembly samples prepared under optimized bonding conditions were characterized by: i) dry electric resistance measurements at selected compression ratios (CR, ranging between 5-45%) and ii) complex electrochemical characterization in a lab-scale vanadium RFB comprising voltammetry techniques, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling, both in a single-cell and two-cells stack. The hot-press bonding of the electrode assemblies significantly improved overall battery performance due to reduced contact resistance (up to 2.5 times comparing to the unbonded one). The performance of the developed electrode assemblies at 10% CR is comparable to the commercial unbonded materials at 20% CR, using bipolar plates with significantly higher content of conductive fillers. Achieved stack parameters with the developed electrodes provided area specific resistance of $2.1 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ (per cell) and the energy efficiency of 86.9% at 40 mA cm^{-2} . The microwave welding allowed significantly faster production of electrode assemblies with similar parameters to hot-press welded ones. The developed electrode assemblies based on low-filled bipolar plates significantly decrease price of battery stack and reduces number of parts during its assembly, which should result in cheaper and more reproducible RFB fabrication.

1. Introduction

Energy from renewable sources is one of the key topic nowadays, aiming to achieve carbon neutrality (EU goal in 2050) for independent and safe energetics [1]. However, production of electricity from renewable sources, such as solar and wind power, is very fluctuating and has to be stabilized. For stabilization of the transition network, various energy storage technologies can be used such as pumped-hydroelectricity energy storage (PHES) or electrochemical storages using Li-ion batteries, hydrogen storage or redox flow batteries. The installed world capacity of

stationary energy storages in 2021 was 192 GW, where more than 90% was covered by PHES, 7.5% were electrochemistry based storages (90% Li-ion) while redox flow batteries accounts only for 1% [2]. Li-ion batteries, so far, play a crucial role among the electrochemical storages due to their high efficiency and energy density, nonetheless the relatively fast capacity decay, high risk of fire and future high demand for the battery in e-mobility motivates the development of alternatives, incl. RFBs. The main advantages of RFBs are safety (non-flammability due to aqueous electrolytes) and flexible scalability (decoupled power and capacity) [3]. So far, the vanadium redox flow battery (VRFB) represents the most developed system, which excels in long life-time (up to 15 000 cycles, 20 years), easy recyclability and residual cost of electrolyte [4]. Long durability is given by the fact that the system contains only single redox active element with different oxidation states on negative (V^{2+}/V^{3+}) and positive side (VO^{2+}/VO_2^+) of the battery, that preventing cross-contamination of the electrolytes and also [5-8].

A typical VRFB single-cell (see **Figure 1**) consists of pairs of end plates, current collectors, bipolar plates (BP) and graphite felt (GF) electrodes, which are sandwiched from both sides of the ion-exchange membrane, which is used to hydraulically and electronically separate the respective half-cells of the battery and minimizes the vanadium ions cross-over, which is the main mechanism of recoverable capacity fade in VRFB [9], while allows for the ionic connection between the half-cells.

Electrolyte distribution and tightness are secured by polymeric distribution flow frames and gaskets. All parts of the battery must meet long-term chemical stability in the aggressive environment of the battery. BP for VRFB stacks is typically manufactured from a composite material composed of suitable chemically stable polymeric binder and carbon-based fillers, where carbon secures the electronic conductivity, and polymer enhances the mechanical and processing properties. Despite various types of BP reported [10], for the application in VRFB mostly carbon/polymer composite based BP are used. These can use different types of polymeric matrix (thermosetting or thermoplastic). Thermoplastic BPs can be produced by various processing technologies e.g. injection moulding, compression moulding or extrusion.

Due to their suitable properties and relatively low price, GFs are mostly used as RFB 3D electrodes. They are industrially produced by carbonization (and/or graphitization) of highly porous polymeric felts (non-woven textile materials). They provide relatively high electric conductivity, high surface area available for electrochemical reactions in RFB and suitable textural properties to serve also as a flow distribution element [11]. For the application in aqueous RFBs, the felt activation is typically required to improve their wettability and to functionalize their surface by oxygen-containing functional groups thus improving their electrocatalytically activity. The activation is typically done by thermal treatment in presence of air [11, 12], although several alternative methods has been reported incl. chemical or electrochemical oxidation. Even for a given electrochemical reaction, the optimal activation conditions (temperature, time) were found to depend on many parameters such as condition of carbonization/graphitization, choice of felt precursors (rayon or polyacrylonitrile), presence of impurities etc. [13, 14]. In case of VRFB, the activation has major influence on negative electrode performance [12], both in terms of initial performance and durability [5].

Figure 1: Schematic of inner design of a single-cell of a redox flow battery. Provided and shown with agreement of Pinflo Energy Storage, s.r.o.

Current collectors, bipolar plates, GF and membranes together with the electrolyte contribute to the inner ohmic resistance of the battery. Depending on the parameters of the used cell components, the ohmic resistance varies from 52% up to 82% of overall VRFB cell resistance [15, 16] and thus has a significant influence on the *EE* of the battery system. Minimization of the ohmic resistance enables to operate the battery at high current densities with low overvoltage (i.e., high efficiency), which enables to decrease the battery size for the required power output that makes the system more economically competitive [17, 18].

Lower ohmic resistance can be achieved by increased compression of the GF and by lowering contact resistances between individual electronically conductive components, particularly between GF and carbon-polymer composite BP. Compression of GF, however, also lowers the porosity of the felts and their permeability for the electrolytes which leads to increased pressure drops and, in turn, to decreased overall efficiency of the system due to increased pumping losses. These effects have been reported in several studies [16, 19-21]. Charvát et al. [16] systematically studied the effect of GF compression on cell resistance and pumping losses, the optimal compression ratio (CR) was evaluated as the minimum of total power losses incl. both pumping losses and cell polarization losses. The optimum was found to be significantly dependent on the felt properties (porosity, precursor polymer), which emphasize the need for proprietary optimization of the cell geometry for the selected active components.

Despite increase compression, several more efficient strategies have been reported for decrease of GF-BP contact resistance without negative impact on pumping losses [22, 23], such as use of: adhesive conducting layer (ACL) between GF and BP [24], integrating BP into the structure of GF

with assistance of soluble resins [22, 25] and thermal laminating/hot-pressing of the components [26]. The integration of GFs and BP into a single electrode assembly, besides decreasing the contact resistance, also reduces the number of components used during the battery stack assembly, thus minimizing the assembly errors and workload.

ACL is a thin graphite-polymeric composite layer with a bulk resistivity lower than that of the carbon-based bipolar plate. It is typically prepared as a mixture of carbon particles (e.g. graphite flakes or fibres) and polymeric binder coated onto the BP surfaces, that significantly reduces the GF-BP contact resistance due to intensified contact between both conductive components at the modified interface. Cao et al. [24] successfully demonstrated preparation of the electrode assembly via use of ACL (middle stack cell electrode, GF/BP/GF), which led to the energy efficiency (*EE*) growth by 4.1 % (to 79.8 % at 150 mA cm⁻²) when compared to the conventional iron-chromium RFB stack assembly. Integrating bipolar plate within the GF structure (end cell electrode assembly) was reported [22], similar principle was used for preparation of middle stack cell electrode assembly [25]. In both cases the contact resistance was decreased and *EE* increased by 7.65 % (to 85.8 % at 100 mA cm⁻²) and 4.85 % (to 81.85 % at 100 mA cm⁻²), respectively.

Both these methods are based on integrating a layer within a GF structure in order to effectively decrease the contact resistance. In contrast, thermal bonding of GF to BP surface seems to be more promising approach as no additional layer is needed and the contact resistance is effectively reduced by simple increase of interfacial area between the carbon fibres of GF and conductive filler within the BP. Thermal bonding is based on the melting of a thermoplastic polymer component of a bipolar plate and its connection with the GF. Hot-pressing method was reported in [26], where the effect of fabrication parameters were studied in terms of applied pressure, time and temperature of the bonding, the optimized procedure resulting in increase of *EE* by 2% (to 84%) when compared to conventional bipolar assembly.

The end electrodes in a battery stack are in direct contact with the respective current collectors (typically copper plates) where another contact resistance is present. As this contact resistance is present only on terminal electrodes of the stack, its overall share on stack resistance is relatively low. On the other hand, the role of CC is to homogeneously spread the current within the entire electrode area, thus homogeneous connection of CC-BP is of high importance. Choe and Lim [27] connected the copper current collector and the bipolar plate with the inserted carbon/epoxy prepreg via a hot-pressing (2 hours, 125 °C). Under optimized conditions *EE* of VRFB single-cell increased by 4.1% (to 82.4% at 100 mA cm⁻²), when compared to the conventional configuration.

In contrast to highly conductive compression-molded commercial bipolar plates used in the mentioned studies, within this study, we have used our own developed extruded bipolar plates. These extruded bipolar plates offer several benefits: on the one hand, the production in a cost-effective, scalable process suitable for series production for the manufacture of bipolar plates in rolls. In addition, the enhanced weldability due to their low carbon filling enables reduction of the number of components for simpler (and thus more precise and cheaper) stack production. The requirements for weldable polymer-based bipolar plates are correspondingly demanding and can be formulated as follows: sufficient chemical and electrochemical stability under battery operation conditions; cost-effective production using processes suitable for serial production; sufficient content of polymeric binder enabling material processing and welding; sufficient content and homogeneous distribution of conductive fillers for high electrical conductivity.

Within our study we focused on the development of the cost-effective electrode assemblies by heat-bonding the GF and CC to BP to mitigate the contact resistance between the mentioned components. The study is divided into three parts describing: i) development of extruded BP with a rich polymeric assay, ii) optimization of hot-press and micro-wave welding methods for heat-bonding of the developed BP with the other components (Two different GFs and two different CC materials were used for preparation of three types of electrode assemblies: GF/BP, CC/BP/GF and GF/BP/GF); iii) complex characterization of the prepared assemblies incl. dry electric resistance measurement and VRFB single-cell and multi-cell stack testing using a complex electrochemical characterization protocol. With the optimized assemblies we achieved significant performance enhancement of the VRFB operation with potential of decreased production costs.

2. Experimental

2.1 Developed extruded bipolar plate

For the preparation of the extrudable BPs (patented by Fraunhofer ICT [28]), polypropylene (Moplen HP500N) was selected as the polymeric matrix and carbon nanotubes (CNT, Cabot), expanded graphite flakes (4 mm particle size, Frenzelit) were selected as graphitic fillers. In the first step, a masterbatch with a CNT content of 6.98% in polypropylene matrix was produced in the compounding process. In the second step, graphite flakes filler was added, and the final proportions were adjusted according to **Table 1**. Several factors had to be weighed against each other: approx. 25 wt.% of polypropylene to ensure weldability of the BP material and the highest possible filling level of conductive components for sufficiently high conductivity. At the same time, the processing properties of the materials must be taken into account, which, based on our experience, can limit the manufacturing processes as the graphite content increases. The compounding was done on a Leistritz 27D twin screw extruder in most cases with 10 kg/h, 800 RPM and 200 °C. The optimal compound composition was as follows: 57 wt.% of expanded graphite flakes, 3 wt.% of CNTs and 40 wt.% of polypropylene.

Bipolar plates with thickness of 1.0 mm were produced under the optimized conditions by extrusion of the Fraunhofer Institute for Process Engineering and Packaging IVV in Freising, Germany. Parameter comparison of the extruded BP and commercial BP (PPG 86 Eisenhuth) are compared in **Table 1**. We can see that the developed extruded BP has 10 times lower through plane conductivity due to the rich polymeric assay. The higher content of PP enables production of thinner BP, which partially compensates the lower conductivity. Moreover, the developed BP is more flexible and lighter and most importantly weldable.

Table 1: Relevant parameters of extruded BP and used commercial BP (according to the [29]). *Measured as sandwich of two gold-plated copper plates at define compression.

BP	Abbrev.	Thickness / mm	Graphite content / wt.%	CNT content / wt.%	Through plane conductivity / S cm ⁻¹	Area specific resistance / mΩ cm ²
Commercial BP	BP _{com.}	2.0	86	-	5.5	12
Extruded BP	BP _{ext.}	1.0	57	3	0.56*	188*

2.2 Manufacture and material for electrode assemblies

Three different electrode assemblies were developed: BP/GF, CC/BP/GF and GF/BP/GF (see **Figure 2** and **Table 2**). For the CC/BP/GF assembly, two different Cu-based CC materials were used: copper foil (0.11 mm thick) and copper plate (2.0 mm thick). Two different GFs based on polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor were used within the study, the list of their relevant parameters is summarized in **Table 3**. The GF1 was provided already activated by the producer and, therefore, it was used as received. The GF2 was activated in our lab by following procedure: a felt sample was placed in a preheated furnace (at 400 °C) without inner air circulation and left there for 1 hour and then taken out. A polymeric-rich skin layer was removed from the BP surface with sandpaper (grit size 1200), followed by cleaning of the surface with propan-2-ol. Two different manufacture approaches were carried out: hot-press welding and microwave welding.

Table 2: List of the electrode assemblies prepared within this study and the components used for their manufacture.

assembly	CC	BP	GF	Welding process
GF/BP	-	BP _{ext.}	GF1/GF2	hot-press
GF/BP	-	BP _{ext.}	GF2	microwave
CC/GF/BP	Cu foil	BP _{ext.}	GF1	hot-press
GF/BP/GF	-	BP _{ext.}	2 x GF1	hot-press

Figure 2: All types of electrode assemblies manufactured in this work: **a)** BP/GF, **b)** CC/BP/GF and **c)** GF/BP/GF. Red lines show the position of the bonding interface between the components.

Table 3: GF materials used within this study and their relevant parameters.

	Producer	Type	Thickness / mm	Precursor	Activation
GF1	AvCarb	G475A	4.75	PAN	Commercial (as received)
GF2	Ceramaterials	GFE 1	6.0	PAN	1 hour, 400 °C, air

Hot-press welding (HPW)

First method used a pneumatic press with heated plates (both top and bottom plates, power output up to 3 kW each), through the plates cooling water was pumped to avoid exceeding set temperature. Aluminium distance frame with a square hole for the GF sample was used to secure the defined compression of GF (in a 15-30% CR range) and to allow sufficient heat transfer from the heating plates to the BP, as well as to prevent bending of the BP during HPW.

The electrode assembly parts (for schematic of set-ups for hot-pressing see **Figure 3a-c**) were placed into the pre-heated hot-press and pressure of 3.2 kPa (for CR of 15%) was applied for a required time. Thin PTFE foils (0.08 mm) were used to protect BP from their direct contact with the surface of the heating plates. Different temperatures, distance frames thickness and times of heating and cooling were tested within the HPW optimization with mostly visual inspection of the bonding quality. Optimized process condition (for GF/BP/GF and GF/BP) were identified as follows: 205 °C for 3 min, followed by cooling until reaching 175 °C, release of the pressure and removal of the electrode assembly and cooling out of the press. Whole process took approx. 20 min. In case of (CC/BP/GF), slightly longer colling phase in the press was necessary until the temperature decreased to 160 °C. To look more closely to the heat transport across the surface of the GF/BP interface during HPW, three thermocouples (K-type 0.5 mm, RS PRO) were placed in the different positions within the GF/BP/GF electrode assembly (schematically shown in **Figure S1**). Thermocouple 1 (T₁) was positioned on the surface of the GF (close to the heat source), T₂ was positioned to the edge of GF/BP interface and on the BP surface, T₃ was placed on the surface of the BP in the middle of the GF (both in terms of width and length). The data were collected using Tevomet TV16 multichannel voltage and temperature monitor (Kolibrík.net).

Figure 3: Cross-sectional schematics of experimental set-ups for the electrode assemblies manufacture by: hot-press welding with individual components used (arrows indicate directions of heat flux and pressure): **a)** CC/BP/GF electrode assembly, **b)** GF/BP/GF electrode assembly, **c)** GF/BP electrode assembly. **d)** Cross-sectional schematics of experimental set-ups for the electrode assemblies manufacture by microwave welding (movement controlled by CNC in y-direction), low pressure used for setting the CR. Gray rectangle represents the frame from polymeric felt for setting the distance to set the required CR.

Microwave welding (MWW)

For the MWW we used a specialized machine constructed by Fraunhofer ICT (for the schematics of microwave see **Figure 3d**). MWW was used only for the preparation of the GF/BP assembly.

GF was placed in the distance frame (with cut area for the GF insertion, similarly, to HPW) made of polymeric felt with reduced thickness to achieve 15% CR. The BP was laid on top of the felt and covered by a polymeric foil, which created an airtight space for assembly compression by a vacuum pump for effective bonding of the components in the assembly. The generated microwaves (2.45 GHz frequency) were passed through waveguide tube and directed to the welded sample by the probe. The probe with approx. width of 1.5 cm was moved above the sample with speed 1 mm s⁻¹ (CNC movement in y-axis, in x and z-axis it was moved manually), power output was max. 350 W for the heating and about 170 W power for holding the temperature on top of the polymeric foil at 160 °C. The temperature on the surface was monitored by thermal camera and based on the response, the power output was regulated. Microwaves were applied to larger area (9 x 9 cm², 5 overlapping lanes driven) than was the GF area (7 x 7 cm²) to secure homogeneous temperature distribution within the bonding area and to have proper connection of the components even at the edges. The entire process took approx. 15 min.

2.3 Dry resistance measurement

The dry resistance was measured for all the manufactured electrode assemblies (see **Table 4**). The apparatus (similar to the [16]) consisting of tensile tester (press, Instron 5544), two insulating plates (made from polyvinylchloride (PVC) and two composite plates PPG 86 (Eisenhuth) is schematically shown in Figure S2. The resistance was measured in a four-point arrangement with a couple of current-sensing and a couple of voltage-sensing electrodes placed on opposite sides of the composite plates. The schematics of electrode assemblies and positions of sensing cables is shown in Figure S3). The measured resistance values were re-calculated to area specific resistance (referred to as dry area specific resistance, ASR_{dry} , assuming 50 cm² active electrode area (i.e. area of GF electrode). ASR_{dry} were measured under GF compression in a CR range of 5-45%.

Table 4: Electrode assemblies and references used for ASR_{dry} measurements. The sign “/” and “+” are used for bonded and unbonded components, respectively.

assembly	reference 1	reference 2
GF/BP	GF+BP _{com.}	-
CC/BP/GF	CC+ BP _{com.} +GF	CC+GF/BP
GF/BP/GF	GF+ BP _{com.} + GF	GF+BP _{ext.} +GF

The dry area specific of single-cell $ASR_{dry-cell}$ of RFB without membrane was measured to determine the share of ohmic resistance created by individual components. The construction of cell is the same as in **Figure S4a** but the membrane was excluded. All the electrode assemblies that were tested in single-cell arrangement were characterized under chosen CR with respected to the electrochemical characterization (detailed description in **chapter 2.4**). $ASR_{dry-cell}$ was evaluated from the slope of the dynamic load curve measured in 0-80 mA cm⁻² current density range by linear fitting.

2.4 Construction of the flow cell and general condition

The prepared electrode assemblies were finally tested in a VRFB, using a single-cell and a two-cell battery stack. In **Figure S4a** the schematics of the flow cell is shown (Pinflow Energy Storage s.r.o.). It consists of aluminium end plates, CC, BP, GF, elastomeric polyolefin-based flat gaskets,

electrolyte distribution frames made of PVC, anion-exchange membrane FAP 450 (Fumatech) assembled in a dry state as received. PPG 86 (Eisenhuth) was used as a reference BP material, to compare battery performance with the manufactured electrode assemblies using the developed BP. The reference VRFB with unbonded GFs have 20% CR, while the VRFB with the developed electrode assemblies have only 10% CR. The geometric area of the electrodes was 50 cm^2 ($7.07 \times 7.07 \text{ cm}^2$). Flow-through distribution of electrolyte was used for both half-cell compartments.

The apparatus (see **Figure S4b, c**) for the testing of the prepared electrode assemblies under the VRFB conditions consisted of a flow cell or stack, diaphragm pump used for the single-cell experiments (KNF) or a peristaltic pump for the stack experiments (Watson–Marlow 323), two separate electrolyte tanks and PTFE tubing connecting the tanks to the cell/stack. Electrolyte tanks were connected to a nitrogen supply to prevent any oxidation of electrolyte species by atmospheric oxygen. The OCV cell (Pinflow Energy Storage s.r.o.), containing PPG 86 carbon-polymer composite electrodes (Eisenhuth) and FAP 450 membrane (Fumatech) was positioned at the inlet of the main cell to monitor the battery state of charge (SoC) during the entire experiment. Each tank contained 0.07 dm^3 of 1.6 mol dm^{-3} vanadium electrolyte (initially equimolar mixture solution of $\text{V}^{3+}/\text{VO}^{2+}$ ions), 2 mol dm^{-3} of H_2SO_4 and 0.3 wt.% of H_3PO_4 . The flow rate of both electrolytes was set to 75 ml min^{-1} . In case of the stack experiments the volume of electrolyte was 0.105 dm^3 and the flow rate was double, i.e. 150 ml min^{-1} . The experiments were carried out at room temperature, that was controlled by air-condition to approx. $22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

2.5 Electrochemical characterization of VRFB

For the characterization of the electrode assemblies in a VRFB single-cell we used a complex procedure consisting of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using Zahner IM6e (Zahner) and dynamic load curves (LC) and galvanostatic cycling using BasyTec GMS (BasyTec GmbH). For the stack characterization different devices were used: for EIS we used potentiostat BSC-815 (Biologic) and for LC and galvanostatic cycling measurements we used potentiostat PTC-520E in combination with Tevomet TV16 multichannel voltage monitor (both Kolibri.net) which enabled voltage monitoring of individual cells during entire experiment.

In both configurations, the battery was firstly characterized by EIS in -50% SoC. EIS was measured at OCV in a potentiostatic mode in the frequency range from 100 kHz (for the stack measurements from 10 kHz) to 50 mHz with a sinus amplitude of perturbing signal of 20 mV . Subsequently, the battery was galvanostatically charged to the theoretical $+50\%$ SoC at a current density of 40 mA cm^{-2} . At this SoC, EIS (same settings as in -50% SoC) and a dynamic LC characterization was performed. The LC measurement was performed by a dynamic current density increase in a range of $0 - \pm 60 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ with a linear increase of $1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Subsequently, galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling of the battery was performed at 40 mA cm^{-2} in $0.8\text{--}1.65 \text{ V}$ voltage range (stack cycling in $1.6 - 3.3 \text{ V}$ range). The last cycle was ended by potentiostatic discharge at 0.8 V (1.6 V for stack measurement) until the current density drops below 10% of the discharging current density (i.e. below 4 mA cm^{-2}). After the cycling, the electrolytes from both tanks were mixed and split to equal volumes, in order to restore the initial electrolyte composition, and the characterization in -50% SoC (EIS) and $+50\%$ SoC (EIS+LC) was repeated.

From the EIS experiments the values of *ASRs* were evaluated; the ohmic *ASR* (ASR_{Ω}), charge transfer *ASR* (ASR_{CT}) and total *ASR* ($ASR_{tot-EIS}$) by fitting the EIS spectra to suitable equivalent circuit model (for equivalent circuit, see **Figure S5**). The charging and discharging area specific resistances (ASR_{LC-ch} , ASR_{LC-d}) were evaluated from the slope of linear part of the corresponding LCs (current density region of 0 – 60 mA cm⁻²). In case of VRFB stack measurements, all the parameters were evaluated for the entire stack as well as for individual cells separately. The characterization was performed at the beginning (initial, INT) of the experiment and after (after, AFT) From the galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling the coulombic and energy efficiency (*CE* and *EE*, respectively) and capacity utilization (*CU*) were evaluated according to std. relations [12] together with their mean values from 10 cycles. *CU* was calculated with respect to the theoretical capacity of the electrolytes according to Faraday's law.

3. Results

The primary aim of this study was to optimize the method for manufacture of highly efficient electrode assemblies with connection of GF, BP and CC. The result section is divided into the two parts: The first part focuses on the manufacturing process of the electrode assemblies by both studied methods, while the second part presents the results of electrical and electrochemical characterization results of the electrodes in both single-cell and 2-cells stack of VRFB.

3.1 Manufacture of electrode assemblies

3.1.1 GF/BP and GF/BP/GF electrode assembly manufacture

Hot-press welding (HPW)

Based on previous research we experienced that commercial BP with high carbon filling cannot be used for heat bonding with GF due to its low polymer binder content (only of 15 wt.% in case of PPG86, Eisenhuth). Thus, the developed extrudable BP were tested for HPW and the process parameters were optimized for the GF/BP assembly and further adopted also for GF/BP/GF assembly. The optimal temperature range for HPW of GF to BP was found to be 190-205 °C. Using lower temperatures either takes too long or it did not provide sufficient connection. Using higher temperatures requires longer cooling times and causes damage, particularly due to the excessive BP melting and its penetration to the GF structure at the edge of GF/BP contact area (not all over the GF/BP interface). This type of damage occurs on both the top and bottom sides of BP where in contact with GF (see **Figure S6**).

Minimal CR of GF during the HPW was set to 15% in order to secure sufficient contact between the components. At higher CRs, the residues of carbon fibers from the disintegrated GF appeared on the PTFE foil after the manufacture process, which indicates the GF damage. Due to high pressure or high temperature the changes of BP thickness appeared, caused by excessive melting of the polymeric matrix. Thus, the optimal conditions range of the HPW process were found out to be relatively narrow. The duration of the cooling phase (reaching chosen temperature before removing assembly from the press) was found to be a crucial parameter, significantly affecting the quality of the bonded BP/GF assembly. Removing the assembly before it was cooled down to 175 °C caused increased surface roughness and bending of BP (see **Figure 4a,b**). Moreover, we observed a deformed BP surface in the area of the connected GF, when compared to the rest of the plate. This damage could lead to electrolyte leakage from VRFB stack and compromise the mechanical integrity of the BP. The GF/BP/GF electrode assembly was manufactured under the same conditions as the GF/BP but using two distance frames (each for individual felt). SEM image of GF/BP cross-section on **Figure 4d** clearly denotes that the connection of GF and BP was effectively created, showing carbon fibers (the lightest objects in the picture) penetrating into the polymeric matrix of the plate (the darkest phase in the picture).

Temperature profiles during HPW are captioned in **Figure 4e**. At the beginning, the temperature rose quickly as the assembly was inserted into the press. After 180 s, the heat source was turned off and the assembly began to spontaneously cool down, still under applied pressure (cooling phase). After approximately 900 s, the temperature reached 175 °C and the assembly was released from the press. After 1000 s, the thermocouples were removed. We can see that the temperature

measured by T_1 (thermocouple located on the outer surface of the felt closer to the heat source) rises more quickly during the heating phase and cools down more slowly during the cooling phase. The T_2 and T_3 thermocouples were positioned to the surface of BP, T_3 in the middle of the felt (in terms of width and length, not depth), while T_2 on the edge of the GF/BP interface (see **Figure S1b**). For T_2 and T_3 , the time to reach a steady state was about 40 s longer than T_1 because of the thermal insulation effect of GF. Thermal insulation property can negatively influence the HPW process for increased electrode area, where the heat transport limitations from a distance frame to the middle of the electrode assembly can result in non-homogeneous temperature distribution within the heat-bonded interface. For our sample dimension, aluminum distance frames sufficiently facilitated the heat transport, but in a real-scale production, with ten times larger electrode areas, this potential issue must be addressed correspondingly.

Figure 4: Images of the prepared GF/BP electrode assembly illustrating: **a)** deformation of BP on GF side due to insufficient length of cooling phase, **b)** deformation of BP on CC side due to insufficient length of cooling phase, **c)** undeformed GF/BP electrode assembly under optimal conditions. **d)** REM image of connection of GF and BP at

200x magnification with a marked cohesive bond in the overlap zone. e) Temperature profile during HPW, thermocouples position specified in the section 2.2.

Microwave welding (MWW)

Alternatively, a different manufacturing process of microwave welding (MWW) was used for the manufacture of GF/BP electrode assembly. The distance frame from the polymeric felt of defined thickness was used to achieve the required GF compression of 15%, which was crucial for creating a homogeneous connection across entire GF/BP electrode assembly. If the thickness was not optimal, we observed depressions or projections at the connection area (similarly to **Figure S6b, c**), although the connection is still created in both cases. With the optimal CR, the GF/BP assembly had a smooth surface, and the cooling times were very fast. The assembly could be handled in less than a minute after the welding, which is much faster compared to the HPW method. The manufacturing process took about 15 min, but it could be significantly shortened with a complete CNC control of the welding machine and by adding more microwave probes to cover the entire active area. MWW is potentially also more suitable for roll-to-roll process implementation on industrial scale. Unfortunately, manufacturing of GF/BP/GF nor CC/BP/GF assemblies was impossible with the MWW machine available for our study. The MWW can also be used only for limited types of materials, for example metals opaques the micro-waves and even the GF can partially absorb them [30], which might disable the bonding of CC. Overall, MWW method seems very promising for the fast production of BP/GF electrode assemblies for RFB stacks.

3.1.2 CC/BP/GF electrode assembly manufacture by hot-press welding

Different strategies were tested to optimize the CC/BP/GF assembly by HPW. The stepwise methods, either connecting CC and BP first and then bonding with GF or connecting BP and GF first and then bonding with CC, were unsuccessful. The first method led to partial disconnection of CC from BP during the second step, while the second method negatively affected the quality of the BP/GF connection. The best approach was to connect all three components in a single step.

Two different CC materials were tested - copper plate (2.0 mm thick) and copper foil (0.11 mm thick). Similarly to the GF/BP assembly, the cooling phase significantly impacted the quality of the CC-BP connection. The cooling phase needed to be extended, with a lower termination temperature of 160 °C, to prevent disconnection of CC due to the tension between CC and BP, most probably caused by the different heat transport rates of the materials (thermal conductivity of copper used for CC and BP is 400 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ and 15 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively) [31]. This issue was more pronounced with the thicker CC copper plate, the connection with the copper foil was better (based on visual observations). The thickness of the copper foil was still sufficient for the homogeneous current distribution during electrochemical characterization. For more details see **Figure S7**.

3.1.3 Dry resistance measurements

The ASR_{dry} of GF/BP electrode assembly **Figure 5a**, (for schemes of the assemblies and sensing cables connection see **Figure S3**) was measured under GF compression in the CR range of 5-45% in two different setups: GF+BP_{com.} (the sing “+” stand for unbonded assembly) and a GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly (extruded BP with polymeric skin layer removed with sandpaper, GF bonded by HPW). From the figures, we can see that bonding of the GF reduces the contact resistance of

GF-BP interface, particularly at low CRs (up to 35%), providing even lower ASR_{dry} when compared to the commercial BP. The ASR_{dry} of GF/BP at 10% CR is thus equivalent to GF+BP_{com.} at 20% CR, which enable to use GF electrodes at lower CR (and thus with lower pumping energy losses). These CR vales were also used in the subsequent VRFB tests.

In **Figure 5b** we present the results of ASR_{dry} measurements for GF/BP/GF, GF+BP_{com.}+GF (commercial reference) and GF+BP_{ext.}+GF (developed unbonded) electrode assemblies. The positive effect of heat bonging of GFs on the reduction of the BP-GF contact resistance is evident from comparison of GF/BP/GF with GF+BP_{ext.}+GF, the unbonded assembly provides significantly higher ASR_{dry} in entire CRs range. At CRs below 25%, ASR_{dry} of the bonded assembly is even lower than for the unbonded assembly based on commercial BP. Thus, even though the developed BP with lower assay of conductive fillers has one order of magnitude lower electric conductivity (see **Table 1**, section 2.1), by heat-bonding them with the GFs and CC, the ASR_{dry} of the resulting electrode assemblies can be comparable or even lower than for the unbonded assemblies using more conductive commercial BP material with higher content of the fillers (by 26%).

Similar comparison is shown in **Figure 5c** for the manufactured CC/BP/GF assembly and two reference electrode assemblies: CC+BP_{com.}+GF and CC+GF/BP. The ASR_{dry} of the CC/BP/GF is significantly lower at low CRs compared to the commercial assembly, which is caused by the reduction of the CC-BP contact resistance. Less flat surface of the developed BP for GF/BP assembly, when compared to the commercial BP, and thus higher CC-BP contact resistance is mostly responsible for the higher ASR_{dry} of the GF/BP even though the ASR_{dry} of this assembly was lower in the previous characterization arrangement (GF/BP measurement).

Figure 5: Development of ASR_{dry} at various CRs of the felt for electrode assemblies: **a)** developed GF/BP_{ext.} and reference GF+BP_{com.}; **b)** developed GF/BP/GF and reference GF+BP_{com.}+GF and GF+BP_{ext.}+GF, **c)** developed CC/BP/GF and references CC+BP_{com.}+GF and CC+GF/BP. The sign “+” is used for unbonded components.

The overview of $ASR_{dry-cell}$ is in the **Table S1**. We can see that the heat bonding of GF to the BP_{ext.} led to the decrease of dry resistance by more than half (from 2.1 to 0.9 $\Omega\text{ cm}^2$). VRFB single-cell without membrane and with BP_{com.} and with CC/BP/GF electrode assembly had the lowest $ASR_{dry-cell}$ among all the tested assemblies. If we compare these dry resistance values for BP_{com.} and CC/BP/GF with the ASR_{Ω} evaluated from EIS in 50% SOC (see **chapter 3.1.6**), we can see that the resistance of the anion-exchange membrane used (FAP-450) creates about 1 $\Omega\text{ cm}^2$ from overall single-cell ASR_{Ω} of approx. 1.5 $\Omega\text{ cm}^2$.

3.3 Electrochemical testing of the electrode assemblies

This section presents the results of our complex electrochemical characterization of the manufactured electrode assemblies in lab-scale VRFB in both single-cell and 2-cells stack set-up. These results are compared to conventional VRFB cell and stack comprising BP_{com.} without the heat-bonding. Based on dry resistance measurements (see previous section) for VRFB with unbonded GFs we used 20% CR of GF, while for the VRFB with the bonded electrode assemblies we used only 10% CR of GF. It's important to note that the Zahner device used for single-cell measurements had cell connected with unshielded cables, which negatively affected the quality of the obtained EIS spectra (due to high contribution of inductance). Therefore, for single-cell measurements (except for the measurement with the developed BPs without HPW), mainly ASR_{LC} values and parameters evaluated from galvanostatic cycling are discussed. For the stack characterization, EIS and LC were measured for each cell separately (and for the stack as a whole), thus the information about ASR_{Ω} and ASR_{CT} from EIS will be discussed more in the stack results chapter.

Due to the gradual initial stabilization of the battery performance caused by membrane swelling and initially fast deactivation of the felt electrodes), only the $ASRs$ after the charge-discharge cycling are discussed. The initial $ASRs$ evaluated from EIS and load curve characterizations are shown in supplementary (**Figure S8–S10**).

3.1.4 Electrochemical characterization in a VRFB single-cell

Figure 6a shows the comparison of voltage profile in the last charge/discharge cycle of the single-cell at current density of 40 mA cm^{-2} for four VRFB single-cell set-ups using following assemblies: $\text{BP}_{\text{com.}}$ (20% CR); $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ unbonded (20% CR); $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ with bonded GF/BP (10% CR); $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ with bonded CC/BP/GF (10% CR). In accordance with dry measurements the cell with the unbonded $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ provided significantly higher voltage plateau separation resulting in lower EE and CU (see **Figure 6c**) due to its higher ASR_{Ω} . The polymer content in the $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ is by 26% higher than in the $\text{BP}_{\text{com.}}$, resulting in high resistance of the BP and BP-GF interface and thus high ASR_{LC} of the cell ($> 3 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$). As shown in **Figure 6b** the cell resistance significantly decreased when the $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ was bonded with GF (ASR_{LC} decreased by $2 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, compared to GF+ $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ assembly) resulting in increased EE by 9.7% and CU by 14.2%. The improved overall performance of VRFB cell with $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ /GF assembly is comparable with $\text{BP}_{\text{com.}}$, even at lower CR of GFs (EE and CU of the commercial cell are only 1.4% and 1.6% higher, respectively, due to lower ASR_{LC} by $1 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$).

For the CC/ $\text{BP}_{\text{ext.}}$ /GF electrode assembly the ASR_{LC} of the single-cell is fully comparable with the cell based on $\text{BP}_{\text{com.}}$, providing an even higher EE by 1.7%. This improvement is clearly related to the reduced contact resistance between CC and BP due to heat-bonding of the components. Importantly, the developed assemblies were tested at lower CRs of the GFs (by 10%) then the reference cell, therefore enabling lower pressure drops and thus lower pumping losses, based on the study by [16]. For all four single-cell arrangements CE values were around 98% and remained stable throughout the cycling, which indicates that the HPW did not negatively affected the selectivity of GF electrode reactions.

Figure 6: Summary of the VRFB single-cell experiment results: **a)** comparison of voltage profiles for galvanostatic cycling (last cycle) for: BP_{ext.} (unbonded), BP_{com.} (unbonded), BP_{ext.} with bonded GF/BP assembly and BP_{ext.} with bonded CC/BP/GF assembly. **b)** ASR_{LC} in +50% SoC evaluated from load curve measurements. **c)** Mean values of (from 10 cycles) coulombic and energy efficiency and capacity utilization. **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 75 ml min⁻¹, charge/discharge current density 40 mA cm⁻², voltage limits 0.8 V – 1.65 V. Load curve measurement current density range 0 – 60 mA cm⁻².

3.1.5 Electrochemical characterization of microwave welded electrode assembly in VRFB single-cell

Different GF (GF2) was used for electrode assembly preparation via MWW and its comparison with HPW method. VRFB single-cells with three different electrode arrangement were tested: a cell with: unbonded BP_{com.}, hot-press welded GF/BP_{ext.} and a microwave welded GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly. In **Figure 7a**, a comparison of voltage profiles during last charge/discharge galvanostatic cycle at 40 mA cm⁻² shows that the cell polarization of all three set-ups is similar, which is in agreement with the ASR_{LC} values shown in **Figure 7b**. The best performance (86% *EE* and 79% *CU*) was observed for the reference cell with BP_{com.}, the cell with microwave-welded GF/BP_{ext.} had *EE* lower by 1.26% at the same *CU*. The hot-press welded GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly provided decreased *EE* by 1.76% with slightly lower *CU* (by 1.14%), possibly due to a minor electrolyte leakage (approx. 2 ml) at the tubing connection during the battery cycling. The *CE* is around 98.5% for all three cell set-ups, thus also here, the GF bonding did not affect electrode reactions selectivity. In general, the performance of a VRFB single-cell with the electrode assemblies prepared by both welding methods was stable and comparable to the reference cell with the unbonded BP_{com.} (again, even at reduced CR of GF by 10% for the bonded assemblies).

Figure 7: Summary of the VRFB single cell experiments results for two different welding methods: **a)** voltage profile of last charge/discharge cycle for BP_{com.} (unbonded) and BP_{ext.} (bonded by HPW and MWW), **b)** ASR_{LC} in 50% SoC evaluated from load curve measurements for the three VRFB set-ups. **b)** Mean values of (from 10 cycles) coulombic and energy efficiency and capacity utilization. **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm^{-3} vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 75 ml min^{-1} , charge/discharge current density 40 mA cm^{-2} , voltage limits $0.8 \text{ V} - 1.65 \text{ V}$. Load curve measurement current density range $0 - 60 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.

3.1.6 Electrochemical characterization of hot-pressed assemblies in VRFB stack

Finally, the prepared electrode assemblies based on BP_{ext.} were characterized in a 2-cells VRFB stack for three different electrode arrangements: stack with unbonded BP_{com.} terminal electrodes (CC+BP_{com.}+GF), stack with partially bonded terminal electrode assemblies (CC+BP_{ext.}/GF), and stack with fully bonded terminal electrode assemblies (CC/BP_{ext.}/GF). Both latter stacks used middle bipolar GF/BP_{ext.}/GF bonded electrode assembly (for stack arrangements see **Table 5**).

Table 5: VRFB stack arrangements tested within the study.

Stack	Terminal electrode	Middle electrode
BP _{com.}	CC+BP _{com.} +GF	GF+BP _{com.} +GF
GF/BP _{ext.}	CC+GF/BP _{ext.}	GF/BP _{ext.} /GF
CC/BP _{ext.} /GF	CC/BP _{ext.} /GF	GF/BP _{ext.} /GF

In **Figure 8d** the distribution of resistances in the stack is shown for all three stack set-ups. The major share of overall cell resistance evaluated from EIS spectra ($ASR_{EIS-tot}$) is created by ASR_{Ω} . The dominant share of ASR_{Ω} on $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ is the same for all three stack set-ups. It is probably due to the relatively thick membrane (50 μm) and its low ion exchange capacity IEC (0.93 meq g^{-1} [32]) required for prevention of vanadium ion cross-over. This was confirmed by the $ASR_{dry-cell}$ measurement (see **chapter 3.1.3**), showing that the membrane is responsible for approx. 1 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell (approx. 2/3 of ASR_{Ω}). The **Figure 8d** shows that the ASR_{CT} was around 0.56 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell for all the stacks. Thus no increase of ASR_{CT} was observed for electrode assemblies, which implies that the HPW (additional heat treatment) did not affect the charge transfer resistance. The stacks using CC+GF/BP_{ext.} electrode assembly (i.e., without heat-bonding of CC) exhibited the highest $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ among the tested arrangements (approx. 2.9 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell), due to high CC-BP_{ext.} interfacial resistance, which corresponds to the results of the single cell characterization. The stack with BP_{com.} had the lowest $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ (2 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell), followed by the stack with CC/BP_{ext.*/GF electrode assembly with slight increase of $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ (by 0.1 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell). The difference between the reference stack with BP_{com.} and developed stack with CC/BP_{ext.*/GF terminal electrode assemblies is thus comparable with the corresponding results of single-cell experiment. The $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ and ASR_{LC} did not differ more than by 5%.}}

The lowest ASR_{Ω} of the reference stack with BP_{com.} are also reflected in the cycling parameters (see **Figure 8a**), EE of 88.3% was even higher when compared to the reference single-cell experiment (86.0%), most probably due to the absence of BP-CC contact resistance in the middle bipolar electrode. Interestingly, CU of the reference stack decreased with the highest slope among the stack experiments of 1.1% $Q_{theor.}$ per cycle. This is most probably due to achieving high SoC within the charging, which increased the driving force for vanadium ion cross-over. The stack with CC+GF/BP_{ext.} terminal electrode assemblies, on the other hand, provided the lowest performance among the tested stacks, with the results corresponding to CC+GF/BP_{ext.} single-cell experiment (with only slightly higher EE by 0.72% at the same CU). In contrast, the stack with CC/BP_{ext.*/GF fully bonded terminal electrode assemblies had only slightly lower EE (by 1.39%) and CU (by 1.89%) than the reference stack (with BP_{com.}). This emphasizes the need for heat-bonding of CC-BP interface for the BP_{ext.} with lower conductivity.}

Closer analysis of the results brings interesting observation: the stack with the CC/BP_{ext.*/GF terminal assemblies initially provided lower EE and CU , which gradually increased over cycling. This trend was not observed in any other experiment. By the end of the cycling experiment, the polarization (also EE) of stack was almost identical as that of the reference stack with unbonded BP_{com.} (see **Figure 8b**). The lower initial efficiency was due to higher initial ASR_{Ω} (2 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ per cell, see **Figure S10b**) which decreased throughout the cycling experiment (as shown by the increasing EE , CU , see **Figure 8a**). Since only ASR_{Ω} decreased over time, while the change of ASR_{CT} was comparable with other measurements, the higher initial ASR_{Ω} is most likely due to slower activation of the membranes in this particular stack (due to the membrane swelling in the electrolyte). The membranes for all the experiments were from the same batch, always new membrane was used for each experiment in the same way (assembled in a dry as received state).}

After the performance stabilization within the charge-discharge cycling, the ASR_{Ω} of the stack (with CC/BP_{ext}/GF electrode assemblies) was comparable to the commercial BP and proportional to single-cell experiment.

Figure 8: Summary of VRFB stack experiments results: **a)** Development of efficiencies and capacity utilization for the reference stack with BP_{com.} and the developed stacks with CC+GF/BP_{ext.} and CC/BP_{ext.}/GF terminal electrode assemblies (using GF/BP_{ext.}/GF middle electrode assembly). **b)** Comparison of last charge/discharge cycle in VRFB stack with different electrode assemblies. **c)** ASR_{LC} per cell in +50% SoC evaluated from load curve measurements. **d)** ASR_{Ω} , ASR_{CT} , $ASR_{EIS-tot}$ per cell in 50% SoC evaluated from EIS measurements. **e)** Mean values (from 10 cycles) of efficiencies and capacity utilization for the individual stack set-ups. **Working conditions:** 1.6 mol dm⁻³ vanadium electrolyte, room temperature, 150 ml min⁻¹, current density of 40 mA cm⁻², voltage limits 1.6 V – 3.3 V. Load curve measurement current density range 0 – 60 mA cm⁻².

3.2 Discussion of the achieved results

In our study the extruded weldable BP material with relatively high polymer content was used, which allowed us to heat-bond with GF by both selected welding methods and with CC using HPW. The BPs production by the continuous process of extrusion together with reduced thickness (less material needed) enables cost reduction of the BP production when compared to the std. compression moulded BP. Moreover, the extruded BP is more flexible, considerably thinner and lighter which also reduces the overall weight of the stack. The connection of GF electrode to the extruded BP significantly reduces ASR_{Ω} by mitigating the contact resistance at GF-BP interface and thus significantly increase overall performance to a level comparable with commercial BP (at higher CR). According to the Charvat et al. [16] the pumping losses (pressure drop) increased by 18% for PAN-based felt (at the same electrolyte velocity) when the CR increased from 10% to 20%, due to the decreased permeability of GF. Thus, the overall battery efficiency (including pumping losses) can be expected to be improved for the VRFB stack with the developed electrode assemblies. Both hot-press and microwave welding methods were successfully demonstrated. Connection of CC led to the decrease of ASR_{Ω} , but more importantly improved the homogeneity of current distribution, which is the main function of CC in RFB stacks.

The highest share of ASR_{Ω} for the cells and stacks tested within this study was created by the anion-exchange membrane used, due to their relatively high thickness (50 μ m) and low IEC (0.93 meq g⁻¹ [32]) required for low vanadium ion permeability. This was confirmed by $ASR_{dry-cell}$ measurements (for single-cell without electrolytes and membrane, as shown in **section 3.1.3**). The

higher resistance of membranes, along with high ASR of unbonded $BP_{ext.}$, led us to the choice of a relatively low current density for galvanostatic cycling of 40 mA cm^{-2} .

Similarly, Choe and Lim [27] reported that the hot-press welding of CC to the BP increased EE by 1.9% (to 82.4% at 100 mA cm^{-2}) when compared to a conventional assembled VRFB single-cell with the extruded BP, and by 4.1% when compared to commercial BPs. The observed improvement is similar to the results obtained within our study. In the mentioned study, only CC was connected to BP via hot-press method using carbon/epoxy prepreg in-between the components with the hot-press manufacture time of 2 hours. In contrast, in our study, no additional material was needed for the bonding and the preparation (including connection of GF) took approx. 30 min using the optimized HPW method.

Another comparison of our results can be done to the study by Kaur et al.[25], where the authors used a single piece of GF for the construction a bipolar electrode, with electrolyte impermeable middle plate created within the GF structure by application of low-viscous epoxy. This assembly was placed into the hot-press for 24 h to create the resulting bipolar electrode. The component resulted in the 28% reduction of ASR_{dry} by eliminating a GF-BP contact resistance. When tested in a VRFB 2-cells stack, they achieved EE of 86.65 % at 50 mA cm^{-2} in the voltage range of 2.4-3.3 V. The experimental conditions and the resulting parameters are thus comparable to our study, despite using a broader voltage range 1.6-3.3 V (which, in general, decreases EE). However, the approach used in the Kaur's study is only applicable for the middle electrode assemblies, while in our study, GFs were also heat-bonded within the terminal electrode assemblies, which makes direct result comparison difficult. Nevertheless, the preparation time in Kaur's study was more than 24 h, whereas, only about 20 minutes in our study using HPW. Reducing manufacturing time is necessary for further cost reduction of VRFB stack fabrication. Our study demonstrated that the HPW method is suitable for the fabricating of both terminal electrode assemblies (including integrating copper-based CC) and the middle bipolar electrode assemblies for RFB at a relatively high production rate. The performance in VRFB showed comparable results to unbonded commercial materials with potential for the reduced costs of the stack fabrication.

4. Conclusions

In this contribution, we developed and studied heat-bonded electrode assemblies for RFB. Two types of terminal electrode assemblies (GF/BP and CC/BP/GF) and one bipolar electrode assembly (GF/BP/GF) were successfully developed. This was enabled by use of own extruded BP with rich polymer phase (40 wt.% of polypropylene) and systematic optimization of the bonding conditions. Two different manufacture processes were successfully carried out, specifically hot-press welding and microwave welding for the bonding of GF to BP. The resistance of the developed electrode assemblies was characterized at a broad CR range under dry conditions, followed by complex characterization in VRFB single-cell and 2-cell stack. Both manufacture processes led to the significant reduction of ASR_Q by mitigating the contact resistances between the individual components (ASR_{Ω} decreased up to 2.5 times for single-cell experiments). The results of experiments with single-cell and stack showed comparable performance of the developed electrode assemblies with the corresponding arrangements based on commercial unbonded BPs. The total ASR of VRFB stack with fully bonded terminal electrode assemblies was $2.1 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ (per cell) and

the EE was 86.9% at 40 mA cm⁻² with significantly higher assay of polymer phase (26%) in BP. The continuous production of extruded BP should enable significant decrease of the production costs, this together with reduced number of components during the stack assembly will decrease the overall costs of RFB stack production which can be easily adopted for various RFB electrolyte chemistries.

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